

On the Effect of Alkali on Oleate and Taurocholate Hemolysis.

By KSHITISH CHANDRA SEN, AMARESH CHANDRA ROY AND
NARENDRA NATH MITRA.

In a previous paper in this *Journal* (Sen and Mitra, 1928, 5, 688) it has been shown that alkali has a peculiar effect on oleate hemolysis. It was observed that under the conditions of the experiment, the presence of small amount of alkali accelerated the hemolysis by oleate when the latter was present in small amounts, but retarded the hemolysis when the latter was present in higher amounts, as compared to pure oleate hemolysis. This behaviour appeared to be a peculiar one and deserved to be further investigated; and we have now come to the conclusion that the observed results given in our previous paper were only a part of a very interesting phenomenon. We have made also some further investigations on the effect of alkali on taurocholate hemolysis and the results will be given in the proper place. The experimental methods are the same as given in our previous papers, the solutions being all made in normal saline. The total volume in each experiment was 5 c.c. and a suspension of sheep corpuscles was used. In Table I, 1 c.c. of a 0.2% suspension was used, the concentration of oleate being 1 in 10,000 and of caustic soda being $N/100$.

TABLE I.*

Amount of oleate in c. c.	Time for hemolysis with oleate in presence of $N/100$ -NaOH in c.c.		
	0.0	0.1	0.2
0.0	—	No hemolysis in 2 hrs.	No hemolysis in 2 hrs.
0.1	20% hemolysis in 1½ hrs.	20% hemolysis in 1½ hrs.	—
0.2	64 mins. 0 sec.	25% hemolysis in 1½ hrs.	No hemolysis in 25 mins.
0.3	29	25% hemolysis in 1½ hrs.	—
0.4	10	57 min. 0 sec.	Partial hemolysis in 25 mins.
0.5	9	50% hemolysis in 1½ hrs.	—
0.6	5	40% hemolysis in 2 mins.	70% hemolysis immediately.
0.7	4	50% hemolysis in 2 ..	—
0.8	3	70% hemolysis in 2 ..	80% hemolysis immediately.
0.9	2	90% hemolysis immediately	—
1.0	2	90% hemolysis immediately	0 min. 52 sec.
1.2	2	0 min. 30 sec.	—

* In this and some other tables, the results expressed as 80 or 90% hemolysis immediately, probably indicated a complete hemolysis of the corpuscles, but accurate determination of the end-point was interfered by the formation of 'ghosts' in the liquid.

TABLE II.

Concentration of corpuscles = 1%, Concentration of alkali = $N/25$.

Amount of oleate in c.c.	Time for hemolysis with oleate in presence of $N/25$ -NaOH in c. c.					
	0.0		0.1		0.2	
0.0	—		5% hemolysis in 4 hrs.		142 mins. 0 secs.	
0.2	No hemolysis in 4 hrs		194 mins. 0 sec.		80	0
0.3	,,		171	0	90	0
0.4	95% hemolysis in 4 hrs.		183	0	87	91
0.5	130 min. 0 secs.		203	0	88	43
0.8	18	24	—		71	10
1.0	15	0	115	0	45	0
1.2	13	2	—		0	34
1.5	11	24	1	14	0	36
2.0	8	9	0	24	Immediate hemolysis.	

TABLE III.

Concentration of corpuscles = 5%. Concentration of alkali = $N/25$.
Concentration of oleate = 1 in 5000.

Amount of oleate in c.c.	Time of hemolysis with oleate in presence of $N/25$ -NaOH in c.c.					
	0.0		0.1		0.2	
1.5	8 min. 27 secs.	30%	hemolysis in 2½ hrs.	70%	hemolysis in 2½ hrs.	
2.0	4	12	,,	,,	3 mins. 12 secs.	
2.5	3	51	24 mins. 26 secs.		2	0
3.0	2	43	70% hemolysis in 1 hr.		Immediate hemolysis.	
3.5	1	40	,,	,,	Immediate hemolysis.	

It will be observed from these tables that excepting some data in Table II, no accelerating action of small amounts of alkali with small amounts of oleate was observed as was found to be the case in our previous paper. An investigation carried out to determine the cause of this difference showed that this phenomenon was probably due to a difference in the temperature in which these two experiments were conducted. Since the present experiments have been carried on at a temperature of 24° and our previous experiments were carried out at a temperature of 32° , we decided to repeat our experiments at the higher temperature and the following table shows a set of results carried out at 32° ,

TABLE IV.

Concentration of corpuscles = 5%. Concentration of alkali = $N/10$.
Concentration of oleate = 1 in 10,000.

Amount of oleate in c.c.	Time of complete hemolysis with oleate in presence of $N/10$ -NaOH in c.c.	
	0.0	0.1
0.0	—	No hemolysis in 4 hrs.
0.8	5% hemolysis in $3\frac{1}{2}$ hrs.	145 mins. 12 secs.
1.0	30% „ „	170 „ 0 „
1.2	118 mins. 0 sec.	175 „ 0 „
1.4	81 „ 0 „	60% hemolysis in 120 mins.

From the foregoing results, it will be observed that the effect of alkali is different with different concentrations of oleate. Thus when the oleate concentration is comparatively small, the hemolytic efficiency of the mixture of alkali and oleate may, under certain circumstances, become greater than that of pure oleate. With medium concentrations of oleate, however, a mixture of oleate and alkali has a markedly lower hemolytic power than the pure oleate. While again with comparatively higher concentrations of oleate, a mixture of alkali and oleate has a markedly greater hemolytic efficiency than the pure oleate itself. Hence when the alkali concentration is constant, we can get either an increase or a decrease of the hemolytic efficiency of a mixture of oleate and alkali depending on the particular concentration of the oleate used. The reason of this peculiar behaviour exhibited by alkali is however not very clear. Another interesting thing to be noticed in the foregoing results is that in the presence of alkali, the time-dilution curves of oleate hemolysis are not always of a simple nature but often show considerable abnormalities. We have repeated our experiments many times and have come to the conclusion that these abnormalities are not due to any experimental error; but are due to some particular conditions such as concentration of the cells, temperature, etc., under which the experiments are made.

So long we have investigated the hemolytic effect of a mixture of alkali and oleate on blood corpuscles. In some previous papers we have shown that normal serum either inhibits or accelerates hemolysis by some chemical hemolytes according to whether it is added together with the hemolyte or after the addition of hemolyte to the cells. The time-interval after which the serum is added to

the hemolyte and corpuscle mixture was also found to be an important factor. Since traces of alkali have been found to have an inhibiting action when added together with another chemical hemolyte in certain concentrations, it was thought desirable to investigate whether alkali, if added to a mixture of hemolyte and corpuscle, could accelerate the hemolysis. This would be interesting because a close similarity in the actions of serum and alkali can be established. In the following table some data of the effect of alkali on oleate hemolysis under different conditions are given.

TABLE V.

Conc. of corpuscles = 0.2%. Concentration of oleate = 1 in 10,000.
0.1 C.c. N/100-NaOH added each time.

Amount of oleate in c.c.	Time of hemolysis with pure oleate.	Time of complete hemolysis when the alkali was added x minutes after the addition of oleate to the cells.		
		$x = \frac{1}{2}$ minute.	$x = 1$ minute.	$x = 2$ minutes.
0.2	23 min 22 secs.	5% hemolysis in 2 hrs.		
0.4	6 8	84 min. 37 secs.	60 min. 0 secs.	2 min. 44 secs.
0.6	3 15	20 28	1 ,, 24 ,, Immediate hemolysis.	
0.8	2 28	2 47	Immediate hemolysis.	
1.0	2 1	1 20	,, ,, —	

It will be observed from this table that the effect of alkali on oleate hemolysis is quite analogous to that exerted by serum. Since serum exerts this inhibitory or acceleratory effect on taurocholate hemolysis also, it was thought desirable to study the effect of alkali on taurocholate hemolysis at this place. In Table VI these data are shown.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of corpuscles = 1%. Taurocholate concentration = 1 in 1,000.
0.1 C.c. N/25-NaOH used each time.

Amount of taurocholate in c.c.	Time of hemolysis with pure taurocholate.	Time of hemolysis when a mixture of alkali and taurocholate was added to the cells.	Time of hemolysis when alkali was added 1 minute after the addition of taurocholate.
1.5	20 min. 5 secs.	55% hemolysis in 2 hours. Immediate hemolysis.	
2.0	12 42	70% ,, ,,	,, ,,
2.5	6 37	80% ,, ,,	,, ,,
3.0	4 50	120 min. 0 sec.	,, ,,

From the foregoing results of the effect of alkali on taurocholate and oleate hemolysis, it is apparent that alkali is behaving in an entirely similar way to that of serum so far as the inhibition or the acceleration of hemolysis is concerned. Since alkali has itself an hemolysing effect at higher concentrations, its action can be better compared to that of an hemolytic serum as studied in one of our previous papers. An important point in connection with this inhibitory or acceleratory effect of serums on taurocholate and oleate hemolysis arises here, namely, to what constituent of the serum is this particular behaviour due? Since normal serum is slightly alkaline, the presence of this alkali would no doubt have a marked action on the observed inhibition or acceleration of hemolysis. In one of our previous papers we have drawn attention of the early work of Sachs (*Biochem. Z.*, 1908, 12, 278) who has shown that the serum proteins have some effect on this particular acceleration phenomenon. Without in any way committing ourselves to any particular hypothesis we may suggest that this acceleration of hemolysis by addition of normal serum may be, at least to a certain extent, due to the alkali content of the serum.

Summary.

(1) An experimental study has been made of the effect of alkali on oleate and taurocholate hemolysis.

(2) It has been observed that in presence of alkali the time-dilution curves of oleate hemolysis show some abnormalities in some cases.

(3) When traces of alkali are added to the cells together with the oleate, it may have either a retarding or an accelerating effect on hemolysis, as compared to pure oleate hemolysis, depending on the concentration of the oleate used. If the alkali is added to a mixture of oleate and corpuscles, a great acceleration of hemolysis can be easily obtained by suitably varying the amount of the oleate and the time-interval after which the alkali is added.

(4) A similar acceleration or retardation of taurocholate hemolysis can be observed in presence of traces of alkali depending on whether the alkali is added before or after the addition of the taurocholate to the cells.

(5) The alkali therefore behaves, in low concentrations, in a similar way as serum and it appears that the accelerating effect of normal serum on taurocholate and oleate hemolysis as studied in our previous papers, may, at least in part, be due to the alkali content of the serum.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT, ALLAHABAD UNIVERSITY

AND

EAST INDIAN RAILWAY LABORATORY, ALLAHABAD.

Received December 22, 1928.